

Web Search on Emerging Topics

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1. Abstract

We are regularly confronted with information on newly *emerging topics*, often linked to current events. Initial encounters with emerging topics can spark curiosity to learn more and, when they involve controversy, form an opinion. One of the primary gateways to do so is web search. However, because the body of knowledge around these topics is still developing, information is often scarce, changes rapidly, and subject to varying interpretations. In addition, there is a lack of implicit feedback such as clickthrough data, which can provide insights into information relevance and quality. These conditions make web searches on emerging topics particularly susceptible to information disorder, driven by system behaviors and human interactions (Golebiewski & Boyd, 2019; Rieger et al., 2024; Wardle & Derakhshan, 2017). However, ensuring that people find high-quality information on emerging topics and controversies and recognize the limits and variability of available knowledge is crucial for informed decision-making and constructive public discourse (Shah & Bender, 2024; Taylor et al., 2018).

With our poster, we present an overview of our research vision towards search environments that facilitate effective knowledge gain, but also foster awareness of the dynamic information space, as well as responsible opinion formation among people searching the web for information on emerging topics. This requires system- and user-centered research, combining quantitative and qualitative methods, theoretical analysis, and participatory design with input from diverse stakeholders and experts (Wagner et al., 2021). In addition to relevant literature and methods for research efforts around web search on emerging topics, we highlight several research challenges that might arise.

We further present an ongoing study with which we want to develop a meaningful and operational definition of *emerging topics* for information behavior and retrieval research. For that, we plan to explore the characteristics of several selected emerging topics on the web. Specifically, we want to investigate how information on these topics, as well as people's interactions with it, evolves over time.

Ultimately, we aim to contribute to a healthy and emancipatory information ecosystem (Mitra, 2025).

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